

The Newly proposed International Academy of Cytology (IAC) Yokohama System for Reporting Breast Fine Needle Aspiration: The Experience of a Single Institution

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Abstract:

Objectives: (1). The newly proposed IAC Yokohama reporting system breast cytology to categorize our samples according to this classification. (2). To assess diagnostic accuracy as well as the diagnostic yield of breast FNAB with corresponding risk of malignancy (ROM) for each category and risk of onsite evaluation (REM).

Materials and Methods: This is a retrospective study of breast cytology cases done at Department of Pathology. A Total of 722 FNA cytology specimens from January 2016 to December 2020 were obtained. These were studied and reclassified according to newly proposed IAC Yokohama system of reporting system of breast cytology into five categories.

Results: Total of 722 cases of breast FNAC, 67(x %) were male and 655 (x %) were females. All the FNAB breast cytology smears were retrospectively reviewed and categorized according to IAC Yokohama system respectively The respective ROM for each category was 0 % for category1 (insufficient material), 3.8% for category 2 (benign), 57.% for category 3 (atypical), 46% for category 4 (suspicious for malignancy), and 99 % category 5 (malignant). Malignant cases were considered only when positive tests, the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and diagnostic accuracy were 94.9%, 99.9 %, 98.6%, 96.1 %, and 98.69%, respectively.

Conclusion: IAC Yokohama reporting system of breast cytology is effective to standardize the reporting in various institutes and provide clear guidelines to clinician for further management.

Keywords: Diagnostic Accuracy, Risk Of Malignancy, Yokohama Reporting System.

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Introduction

Breast cancer is the most common malignancy among women in the world. It also happens to be the most frequent cause of death in women especially in developing countries, thus making both screening and early detection crucial factors in lowering the mortality rate. As we know with the advent of triple testing for breast malignancies, fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) plays a vital role in the evaluation of any suspicious breast lesion. It is a cost effective, minimally invasive and rapid technique, which helps play a role in early detection. Due to overlap of cytomorphological features of both benign and malignant breast lesions to a significant extent, differentiation in all cases is not possible. To tackle these grey zone areas of uncertainty and to bring about a degree of uniformity to the reporting system, The Yokohama System for Reporting Breast Cytopathology has proposed a five-category classification, Category 1- insufficient material;

Category 2- benign; Category 3- atypical, probably benign; Category 4- suspicious for malignancy, probably in situ or invasive carcinoma; and Category 5- malignant

Aims and Objectives:

1. The newly proposed IAC Yokohama reporting system breast cytology to categorize our samples according to this classification
2. To assess diagnostic accuracy as well as the diagnostic yield of breast FNAB with corresponding risk of malignancy (ROM) for each category and risk of onsite evaluation (REM)

Materials and Methods:

This is a retrospective study of breast cytology cases done at Department of Pathology. A Total of 722 FNA cytology specimens from January 2016 to December 2020 were obtained. These were studied

and reclassified according to newly proposed IAC Yokohama system of reporting system of breast cytology into five categories. The risk of malignancy and risk of onsite evaluation, sensitivity, specificity, were calculated accordingly and diagnostic accuracy were estimated on the basis of the final histopathological correlation in available cases

Results

Total of 722 cases of breast FNAC, 67(x %) were male and 655 (x %) were females. All the FNAB breast cytology smears were retrospectively reviewed and categorized according to IAC Yokohama system respectively In 722 cases 67 were male and 655 were females. M: F 1:10. 201 cases had histopathological correlation, of which 75 were malignant lesions.

C1. Insufficient material 11% (n=80).

C2. Benign 63% (n=462)

C3. Atypical probably benign 1% (n=7),

C4. Suspicious for malignancy 4% (n=32)

C5. Malignant 19% (n=141)

The respective ROM for each category was 0 % for category1 (insufficient material), 3.8% for category 2 (benign), 57% for category 3 (atypical), 46% for category 4 (suspicious for malignancy), and 99 % category 5 (malignant). Malignant cases were considered only when positive tests, the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and diagnostic accuracy were 94.9%, 99.9%, 98.6%, 96.1%, and 98.69%, respectively. The respective ROM for each category was 0% for category1 (insufficient material), 3.8% for category 2 (benign), 57% for category 3 (atypical), 46% for category 4 (suspicious for malignancy), and 99% category 5 (malignant).

Table 1:

Yokohama Category	Risk of Malignancy
Insufficient/Inadequate	0%
Benign	3.8%
Atypical	57%
Suspicious for malignancy	46%
Malignant	99%

The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value , and diagnostic accuracy were 94.9%, 99.9 %, 98.6%, 96.1 %, and 98.69%,respectively.

Category 1: Insufficient/inadequate material

Category-2: Benign

Benign: hyperplastic ductal epithelial tissue fragment with bimodal cells arranged in monolayered sheets and small cohesive clusters. These clusters comprised of round to oval ductal epithelial cells and spindle shaped myoepithelial cells at periphery. Background shows bare nuclei and stromal fragments.(Giemsa,×100).

Category 3: Atypical

Atypical: ductal epithelial cells arranged in small clusters structures along with spindle shaped myoepithelial cells. Some of these cells show mild anisonucleosis with proteinaceous background. (Giemsa, ×400).

Category 4: Suspicious of Malignancy

Suspicious of Malignancy: loose clusters and singly scattered polygonal cells with central to eccentrically located nuclear, irregular nuclear chromatin and moderate amount of cytoplasm. (H&E, ×400).

Category 5: Malignant

Malignant: sheets and clusters of ductal epithelial cells. These cells are polygonal and show pleomorphic nuclei with open chromatin. The nuclear contours are irregular. Cytoplasm is moderate, eosinophilic. (Giemsa, ×400)

Discussion

The IAC Yokohama System of reporting defines five categories for the standardization of reporting breast fine needle aspiration biopsy cytology. This study shows that the utilization of these categories produces better results and provide vital information for the treating clinician 1 case was reported as category 5 as duct cell carcinoma but on correlating with the final histopathology report it was diagnosed

as duct papilloma. In a similar study done by Chauhan et al., the sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive value and diagnostic accuracy were found to be 98.90%, 99.16%, 97.82%, 99.58% and 99.09% respectively, which were similar to our findings. They were able to conclude that FNAC is a simple, reliable, cost effective tool and when coupled with physical examination and imaging studies (triple approach), FNAC can be a highly sensitive diagnostic tool.

They stated that if a universally acceptable standardized reporting system for breast cytology is

adopted, it could enhance the diagnostic accuracy of FNAC

Table 2: Comparison with other studies

Statistical parameters	Poornima v et al.	Chauhan et al.	Present study
Sensitivity	94.59	98.90%	94.9%
Specificity	98.99	99.16%	99.9%
Positive predictive value	98.59	97.82%	98.6%
Negative predictive value	95.74	99.58%	96.1
Diagnostic accuracy	96.97	99.09%	98.69%

Conclusion

The present study showed statistically significant sensitivity, specificity, and diagnostic accuracy, especially with malignant cases. Hence, using the IAC Yokohama reporting system of breast cytology is effective to standardize the reporting in various institutes and provide clear guidelines to clinician for further management.

References

- Vetto J, Pommier R, Schmidt W, et al. Use of the "triple test" for palpable breast lesions yields high diagnostic accuracy and cost savings. *Am J Surg.* 1995;169:519-522.
- Dong J, Ly A, Arpin R, Ahmed Q, Brachtel E. Breast fine needle aspiration continues to be relevant in a large academic medical center: experience from Massachusetts General Hospital. *Breast Cancer Res Treat.* 2016;158:297-305.
- Masood S, Rosa M, Kraemer DF, Smotherman C, Mohammadi A. Comparative cost-effectiveness of fine needle aspiration biopsy versus image-guided biopsy, and open surgical biopsy in the evaluation of breast cancer in the era of affordable care act: a changing landscape. *Diagn Cytopathol.* 2015;43:605-612.
- Cobb CJ, Raza AS. Obituary: alas poor FNA of breast? We knew thee well!? *Diagn Cytopathol.* 2005;32:1-4.
- Boerner S, Fornage BD, Singletary E, Sneige N. Ultrasound-guided fine-needle aspiration (FNA) of nonpalpable breast lesions: a review of 1885 FNA cases using the National Cancer Institute-supported recommendations on the uniform approach to breast FNA. *Cancer.* 1999;87:19-24.
- Layfield LJ, Bentz JS, Gopez EV. Immediate on-site interpretation of fine-needle aspiration smears. *Cancer.* 2001;93:319-322.
- Nassar A. Core needle biopsy versus fine needle aspiration biopsy in breast-a historical perspective and opportunities in the modern era. *Diagn Cytopathol.* 2011;39:380-388.
- Bonaccio E, Calhoun KE, Camp M, et al. NCCN Guidelines Panel Disclosures. NCCN Guidelines Version 1.2019 Breast Cancer Screening and Diagnosis. 2019.
- Cardoso F, Kyriakides S, Ohno S, et al. Early breast cancer: ESMO clinical practice guidelines for diagnosis, treatment and follow-up. *Ann Oncol.* 2019;30:1194-1220.
- Palombini L, Fulciniti F, Vetrani A, et al. Fine-needle aspiration biopsies of breast masses. A critical analysis of 1956 cases in 8 years (1976-1984). *Cancer.* 1988;61:2273-2277.
- Vetrani A, Fulciniti F, Di Benedetto G, et al. Fine-needle aspiration biopsies of breast masses. An additional experience with 1153 cases (1985 to 1988) and a meta-analysis. *Cancer.* 1992;69:736-740.
- Wells CA, Ellis IO, Zakhour HD, Wilson AR. Guidelines for cytology procedures and reporting on fine needle aspirates of the breast. *Cytopathology.* 1994;5:316-334.
- Field AS, Schmitt F, Vielh P. IAC standardized reporting of breast fine-needle aspiration biopsy cytology. *Acta Cytol.* 2017;61:3-6.
- Field AS, Raymond WA, Rickard M, et al. The International Academy of Cytology Yokohama System for reporting breast fine-needle aspiration biopsy cytopathology. *Acta Cytol.* 2019;63:257-273.
- Fischer AH, Benedict CC, Amrikachi M. Five top stories in cytopathology. *Arch Pathol Lab Med.* 2013;137:894-906